

HI-TEK – An interactive career guide for Technological University of the Philippines Manila

Mervin G. Sanding*

School of Business and Computer Studies, St. Dominic College of Asia

*Corresponding author: mgsanding@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

Choosing a career is an important part of any youth's life. The college degree that they will be choosing ultimately may dictate their future. The arrival of the K-12 programs, allows students to align their senior high school track to their college course. Technological University of the Philippines (TUP) is one of the leading state university that offers extensive and diversified courses, primarily involved in technology-based industry. However, as easy as it seems, choosing one, is never an easy decision. Various factors may lead to or even mislead students with their course selections. It may be with parents selecting a course for their children, or sometimes the apprehension of inquiring about available courses to the admission office. The goal of this study is to create an interactive career guide that aligns the K-12 Track to courses being offered by TUP – Manila. In this study, Hi-Tek: Interactive Career Guide involves a quantitative method. The proponents utilized this method to gather numerical data from questionnaires to the respondents and quantify this to determine the important elements and components which were added to the design concept. The mobile application can easily be downloaded and installed on any mobile phone and tablet. Users have full control with the navigation as they select their K-12 track and would lead them to the aligned courses that are available in TUP-Manila, essentially learning course description and career opportunities of the selected course. The mobile application integrates strong visual and animation, music, and interactive/responsive navigation buttons that the current generation are familiar and comfortable with. Timely with the changes of the new normal, the application would aid TUP as well in course inquiry as this may be facilitated online. The respondents' overall evaluation on aesthetic is 4.53 average mean, which can be interpreted as Excellent. The respondents' overall evaluation on functionality is 4.47 average mean, which can be interpreted as Very Good. The respondents' overall evaluation on quality is 4.64 average mean, which can be interpreted as Excellent. The results gathered from the respondents confirms that the development and facilitation.

Keywords: Technological University of the Philippines – Manila, interactive career guide, mobile app.

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Introduction

Among the challenges and decisions that youth encounter in their lives, career selection is deemed most important and challenging decision they have to create. Understanding and selecting the right career will greatly affect their lives. Career choice is important in the developmental stage of youth as not only it will dictate their career, but it will bear significance in their psychological, physical, and socio-economic well-being beyond their youthful age into their adult life (Bubić & Ivanišević, 2016).

The career decision of youth requires a process of understanding what they want to do with the aid of guidance and planning. A research conducted regarding about parent's educational and finance was viewed as among the factors that dictates the career decision of students. Often, parents know what is best for their children. But it does not necessarily mean that parents will be deciding the career of their children as choosing a career is an individual decision that all youth will have to make. Personal interest is a major factor that influenced career choice. The trend of individualism is on a continual upward trajectory among the current generation known as Gen Z. Today's generation is more independent in their decision making as this affirms their identity and individuality among their peers.

Generation Z, the next generation after the millennials, is described as the generation of people who were born from the mid-1990s through the second decade of this century, although precise years vary according to the source. This generation is the generation where technology and the internet are already at boom. At an early age, they already have smartphones and other gadgets at hand, the internet is very accessible to most people, affordable to some but just a rare case to some people who do not have internet due to the area's lack of accessibility or because of poverty. But, in general, the internet is at the palm of their hands. With this, teens nowadays are exposed to social media, such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube. They used the internet to share information about themselves, gain and access information, and interacting with different people including strangers and people across the globe.

At the Raising Gen Z: Zentennials conference last 2017, they described Gen Z as “Highly Connected,” “Thrive on Acceleration,” and “Independent” (Diaz, 2017). Highly connected in terms of communications, thrive on acceleration, they want fast and easy, and independent people - lack of nature-oriented community due to social media. They prefer to be alone in their room and connect through social media. But despite that, Gen Z has a lot of potentials, because not only they are tech-savvy they are also digital-savvy, and they grew up with computers and the internet. Their confidence in their tech skills was learned through technology.

The rise of the digital revolution has greatly affected our function especially today's youth, evidently in the endless integration of technology with our way of living. The use of mobile and electronic devices aids us in common tasks such as communication, shopping, reading, finding direction, and information (Goodman et al., 2016). Greater access and demand for technology have presented solutions to various operations and services (Gandhi & Patel, 2018).

The integration of technology into teaching and learning is not a new thing in education. Before the introduction of the internet and computers, the use of audio and video presentations was the primary platform for replacing traditional instructional delivery methods according to Kaware and Sain (2015). But since the invention of the internet and moving into new leaped of the century, 2000 and onwards, technology became a tool as a primary source of information. Students have a deep understanding of how technology can transform the way we work and live. The job opportunities and a career involving technology appeal to Gen Z particularly information technology and systems development.

A mobile interactive career guide would assist a youth, specifically Gen Z with creating a clear path of decision making for their ideal course to pursue in college (Fahrer, 2016). The availability of digital information is a platform that the current generation is appealing and highly suitable for their needs (Aseeri, 2013; Phadung, 2015; Pugnali et al., 2017). Students thrive on efficiency, comfort, and innovation for gathering information (Jolly, 2003; Lopez-Moreno et al., 2013).

Conceptual Framework

In the input phase, where the data gathering will happen. All the data related to Gen Z will be gathered from related literature and studies, this is to identify the needs and requirements for Gen Z and applied to the program. This will also include understanding information technology, the significance of utilization of technology, audio-visual, and interactive navigation buttons (Baglama et al., 2018; Bakker et al., 2015; Coombes et al., 2019; Friedrich, 2002; Jimenez, 2007; MacEachren & Taylor, 2013). Understanding the K-12 tracks and collecting all the course descriptions and job opportunities are both important with the development of the program as well.

In the process phase, information gathered was significantly considered in the designing of the program. Both aesthetics and functionality of the program needed to be equally applied. The introduction of the official mascot, Tek, a gray hawk, as the digital tour guide of the program. The program also featured significant places and colleges that would introduce incoming students how the university looks like.

The creation of a flowchart that identifies which specific K-12 Tracks does a course belongs to. This would essentially trim down the selection of a course of student users to utilize their prior track in senior high school. The use of various Adobe software such as Adobe Photoshop, Adobe Illustrator, and Adobe Animate was necessary with the design and development of the programs as illustrations and animations were collectively combined to create the program.

In the output phase, Hi-Tek an interactive career guide will be the desired output. This will allow students to get information about the available courses in TUP-Manila. Aside from that, the program also assists in aligning prior K-12 track in senior high school with specific compatible courses (Kapaj, 2018). The high utilization of audio, visual, and responsive navigation would benefit all types of learners. The output will undertake revisions based on the evaluation (Choi et al., 2013).

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

Statement of the Problem

The study aims to develop a Mobile Interactive Career Guide Application that would assist students in selecting ideal course in Technological University of the Philippines – Manila. The research also aims to recognize significant factors and hindrances experienced by the senior high students in college. Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the factors that pose hindrance to senior high school students in selecting their ideal course in TUP-Manila?
2. How could the manual assist the senior high school students to figure out their preferred college course?
3. What are the specifications of the career guide that can be deployed to attract the interest of students in using the application?
4. What are the respondents appraisal of the interactive career guide with the following criteria?
 - 4.1 Aesthetics
 - 4.2 Quality
 - 4.3 Functionality

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the formation of the Hi-Tek: Interactive Career Guide involves a quantitative method. The proponents utilized this method to gather numerical data from questionnaires to the respondents and quantify this to determine the important elements and components which were

added to the design concept. This affected the proponents with their creation of the design, considering the results coming from the questionnaires.

Figure 2. Program page

This study was classified to be descriptive research due to its nature of studying characteristics of a population corresponding to the existing hindrance in career decision making. The purpose of the study is to assure that the current generation; specifically, Generation Z will be a vital participant in the development of the digital career guide.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Technique

The respondents of this study are composed of one hundred (100) students from different schools that the researchers will choose using a random sampling technique thus selection of participants is an unbiased representation of the total population. The availability of the participants will be considered in the selection process.

Description of the Respondents

The respondents of the study should be those under "Generation Z" or people that are born from 1995 to 2012. The respondents would be composed of one hundred (100) students, age range from 15 years old to 20 years old. Respondents may be male or female.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire will be distributed as a 5-point Likert scale type questionnaire towards the respondents. The quantitative responses for the questionnaire will include a five (5)-point Likert scale composed of excellent, very good, good, fair, and poor. The survey instrument was validated by the Research Conductors themselves.

Table 1. Rating scale criteria

Rating	Remarks
4.50 – 5.00	Excellent
3.50 – 4.49	Very Good
2.50 – 3.49	Good
1.50 – 2.49	Fair
1.00 – 1.49	Poor

The remarks were based on the following criteria:

Aesthetic. Visual elements of the output

Functionality. The usefulness of the output

Quality. Overall feel and efficiency of the output.

Data Gathering Procedure

From the selected population of the respondents and the research instruments, the source of data was derived from the questionnaires given to the Generation Z students. The participating respondents were randomly chosen based on their availability and accessibility. The students would then test out the Digital Career Guide and rate the questionnaire based on their experience with the study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical tools applied to interpret the data include the average arithmetic mean and the percentage. The average arithmetic mean was used to find out the average of the responses in five (5) options, namely (5) excellent, (4) very good, (3) good, (2) fair, (1) poor which was used to rate the acceptability of the prototype. On the other hand, the percentage was used by the researcher in treating the profiles of the respondents and prototype features recommendation.

Results and Discussion

The survey facilitated involved one hundred (100) respondents, all Grades 11 and 12 students, age ranging from 16 to 20 years old. These students are coming from different K-12 tracks/strands such as Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM), Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM), Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL), and Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMMS). These students, specifically Grade 12 students, will be looking for courses to take in college.

Based on the conducted study, majority of the respondents found it challenging to choose a course in TUP-Manila due to unavailable course description and job opportunities. It is also worth note taking that several factors such as some are reluctant to ask information in the admission office and parents selecting the course for their children. The study also revealed how could an interactive career guide assist students to figure out their preferred courses in TUP-Manila. Respondents would like to have a K-12 track and aligned course available. This is to connect their prior senior high track/strand with the available courses in TUP-Manila.

Respondents would like to have course description and job opportunities easily accessible for them. In terms of the specifications of the career guide that can be deployed to attract the interest of students in using the application, majority of respondents seek animated visual illustrations, easy navigation interface, and responsive navigation buttons come next to their considerations with the features. Considering the generation of the respondents, it is highly recommended to use technology as means of information.

The result on respondents' evaluation were very positive. The respondents' overall evaluation on aesthetic is 4.53 average mean, which can be interpreted as Excellent. The respondents' overall evaluation on functionality is 4.47 average mean, which can be interpreted as Very Good. The respondents' overall evaluation on quality is 4.64 average mean, which can be interpreted as Excellent.

Conclusion and Recommendations

With the collected studies and data from the survey, the researcher concludes that Hi-Tek: An Interactive Career Guide for Technological University of the Philippines – Manila was evaluated excellent. The respondents' evaluation of the interactive career guide in terms of aesthetics and quality were both excellent, while evaluation in terms of functionality was very good. The Mobile Interactive Career Guide Application will conveniently provide students with career selection as it is accessible through mobile phones which younger generations prefer rather than asking and counseling. This lessens or possibly eliminates hindrances of students selecting courses in TUP-Manila. Furthermore, this allows the institution to efficiently introduce courses to different students without actual and physical interactions.

It is recommended that future researchers may develop a 3D version of the application. This may include a virtual map of the physical structure of the schools. They may integrate optional enable/disable voiceover if found necessary to apply in certain parts. They may develop a website application that students may access on their computers without downloading. Availability of the application to Google Play Store should be implemented.

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